

From Awareness to Action: Light Pollution in Serbia Today

Plenary Lecture

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Abstract: Light pollution in Serbia is one of the growing yet largely unrecognized environmental challenges, primarily due to a lack of visibility within the existing institutional and legislative framework. Hence, the first wave of raising awareness among the public and decision-makers began around 2016 and followed a "bottom-up" approach, mainly leaning on astronomy enthusiasts and various NGO's that guided the movement, with NGO "Carpe Noctem" in the lead. Their efforts were first recognized by the Center for Science Promotion (part of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation), which provided funding for diverse educational content, such as night hikes, brochures, astronomy camps, and video materials. Shortly after, from 2018 to 2023, a group of researchers from the Faculty of Sciences in Novi Sad implemented two projects (Vobanista and Electra) within the Interreg-IPA Cross-border Cooperation Programme Hungary-Serbia, recognizing the touristic potential of dark skies in the border area between the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina and the Bács-Kiskun region in Hungary. In time, many other researchers have engaged with this topic, resulting in two major projects, funded by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, which can be considered as the beginning of institutional efforts to lay the foundation for systematic monitoring and understanding the problem of light pollution in Serbia. The UrbObsBel project is carried out by the Astronomical Observatory of Belgrade and partnering institutions, and its primary goal is to assess the distribution of light pollution in urban (Belgrade) and rural environments (Vidojevica), thus investigating the relationship between urbanization processes and the rise of artificial light at night, using various instruments for monitoring. On the other hand, the Enlight project, led by the Institute for Biological Research "Siniša Stanković", National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, has researched the biological effects of artificial light at night towards specific amphibians that are considered to be photobiologically sensitive to light pollution. Besides scientific endeavors, there is also an effort to establish the first Dark Sky Park at Mountain Vidojevica, which has the only astronomical station for scientific observations in Serbia, together with many others that followed suit, trying to protect the natural darkness at Jastrebac Mountain and Rajac. Still, despite the existing institutional and non-institutional efforts, light pollution needs to be formally recognized and incorporated within the legal framework so that concrete measures and strategies can be developed in order to protect the dark skies in Serbia.

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